

INFLUENCE OF SALINITY ON THE EARLY STAGES OF THE AFRICAN CATFISH
HYBRID (*Clarias gariepinus* x *Heterobranchus bidorsalis*)

¹Gbulubo, A. J., ²Gabriel, U. U. and ²Deekae, S. N.

¹African Regional Aquaculture Centre, Nigerian Institute for Oceanography and Marine Research, P M. B 5122, Port Harcourt, Nigeria, ²Department of Fisheries and Aquatic Environment, Rivers State University of Science and Technology P. M. B 5080, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Salinity tolerance tests were conducted on the hatching and survival of eggs and seven day-old fry of African catfish hybrid (*Clarias gariepinus* x *Heterobranchus bidorsalis*). The percent hatchability of eggs in various incubation salinities ranged between 62.3% to 30.5% from 0ppt to 8ppt, with an optimum range of 0-4ppt. Hatching increased with time, but declined with increase in salinity level, and there was no hatching in 10ppt. The median lethal salinity (MLS-96) of the fry was 4.39ppt whereas the median lethal time for 10ppt was 2.24hrs. The cumulative mortality of the fry transferred into various salinities increased with exposure salinity and duration. Water temperature values ranged from 23°C to 27°C, dissolved oxygen ranged from 6.2mg/l to 6.8mg/l while pH ranged from 5.6 to 6.6.

KEYWORDS: African catfish hybrid, salinity, egg, seven day-old fry.

INTRODUCTION

Two clariid catfishes, *Clarias gariepinus* (Burchell, 1822) and *Heterobranchus bidorsalis* (Geoffrey St Hilaire, 1809) are prominent in African aquaculture. They possess air-breathing mechanisms, are hardy in nature and by virtue of their suitable reproductive strategy and nutritional efficiency attain large size within a short time (Huisman and Richter, 1987, Hecht *et al.*, 1988, Haylor, 1989). Clariid catfishes are also good potential subjects for brackish water aquaculture (Gbulubo and Erundu, 1998; Fashina-Bombata and Busari, 2003; Iyaji, 2008). In addition, they have very wide range of diets which include most living organisms. The advantage of this food habit is the ability to adjust to the food items that will occur in a brackish water system (Clay, 1977).

In the Niger Delta, there is an estimated 730, 240 hectares of extensive saline swamps (Pillay, 1973). The swamps hold enormous potential for aquaculture and in most areas are yet to be fully explored. This is partly due to inadequate knowledge of many cultivable fish species that are suitable for brackish water culture. Studies have been conducted involving the transfer of fish from one salinity regime to another (brackish water) using known freshwater fishes. These studies are all directed at finding fishes already intensively farmed in freshwater that can survive and grow in brackish water environment. Few of such works are, salinity tolerance of the fry of *Oreochromis niloticus* (Watanabe *et al.*, 1984) in which the spawning salinity of the fry increased with salinity tolerance of the fry. Studies with *Heterobranchus longifilis* in Ebrie Lagoon (Ivory Coast), showed that the fish was suitable for culture in low salinity ≤ 7 ppt water bodies (Legendre, 1986). Bringolf *et al.*, (2005) in their salinity tolerance study with juveniles of flathead catfish *Pylodictis olivaries*, reported that the fish could be cultured in brackish waters (8-11ppt).

There is therefore the need to investigate the salinity tolerance of this freshwater farmed fish, especially the early developmental stages, which form the basis for consideration of its culture in brackish water. This study was therefore designed to investigate;

1. The effect of salinity on the hatchability and survival of the eggs of the fish.
2. The salinity tolerance limit of seven day-old fry.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out in the fish hatchery and laboratory of African Regional Aquaculture Centre (ARAC), Aluu, near Port Harcourt during the raining season of 2007.

Brood *C. gariepinus* and *H. bidorsalis* used for the study were obtained from a private fish farm at Aluu, and identified as described by Teugels *et al.*, (1990) and Teugels (1996). Gravid female of *C. gariepinus* of

mean weight of 800 grams were injected with ovaprim. Dosage was based on manufacturer's prescription of 0.5ml/kg body weight of fish and administered as described by Okoro *et al.*, (2007). Ovulated eggs stripped from induced females were collected in a plastic bowl. Brood males of *H. bidorsalis* of mean weight of 1.2kg were scarified and the testes dissected out. Edges of the testes were cut open with blade and milt washed into a 0.9ppt saline solution. This was gently and thoroughly mixed.

Fertilization was effected with addition of freshwater to the mixture of the stripped egg and milt, as described by Nwadukwe (1995).

Test Solutions

Six different solutions were prepared by weighing 2,4,6,8 and 10 grams of Sodium chloride with Labtop balance (Yamato LE 180, Yamato Scientific Co Ltd., Tokyo, Japan). Each salt portion was dissolved in a litre of freshwater to obtain 2,4,6,8 and 10ppt respectively. Freshwater was used as control (Oppt)

Salinity Tolerance Test on Fertilized Eggs

Hundred fertilized eggs were introduced into a 600ml beaker containing 300ml of each of the test solution. Five test solutions were used (2, 4, 6, 8 and 10ppt) with freshwater (Oppt) as control. Each treatment level was in three replicates. Water temperature, dissolved oxygen (DO) and pH were determined. Hatchability of the eggs was monitored by counting the hatchlings in each treatment at hourly interval for nine hrs.

Rearing of Experimental Fish

Fertilized eggs of *C. gariepinus* x *H. bidorsalis* were incubated in trays (30cm x 45cm) with mosquito netting in a rectangular concrete tank (2m x 4m) containing freshwater. The hatched larvae were nursed in the concrete tank. The larvae were fed with *Atermia* after the absorption of the yolk sacs up to the seventh day.

Salinity Tolerance Test on Seven day-old fry.

Ten fry each of the seven day-old fry (0.8 ± 0.12 cm) were introduced into each five litre plastic aquarium containing two litres of the different test solutions (2,4,6,8 and 10ppt). Each exposure and control was in four replicates. Freshwater (Oppt) was used as control. The fry were not fed throughout the experimental period. Mortality was monitored for 4days (96hrs). Dead fry were counted and recorded. Water temperature, dissolved oxygen and pH were determined. Test solution in each aquarium was changed daily. A fry was considered dead when it did not respond or react to gentle prodding with a feather.

Water Quality Parameters

Mercury in glass thermometer was used to measure the water temperature during incubation of the eggs and salinity tolerance of the fry, Hydrogen ion concentration (pH) was determined with a pH meter (Hannah Instruments Portugal, HA Model 191), Dissolved oxygen was determined using Winkler method (APHA, 1998) while Salinity was determined by a Refractometer (ATAGO S/Mill E).

Analysis of Data

Probit analysis (Finney, 1978) was used to determine the median lethal salinities (MLSs) and median lethal times (MLTs). Mortality and hatchability data at the various concentrations and duration were subjected to ANOVA and differences among means separated by Duncan multiple range test (Wahua, 2010).

RESULTS

Hatchability of *C. gariepinus* x *H. bidorsalis* eggs in various incubation salinities

The hatchability (%) of egg in various incubation salinities ranged between 62.3% and 30.5% (Oppt to 8ppt) respectively. Higher hatchability of 62.3% and 61.9% were recorded in Oppt and 4ppt respectively at 32hrs (Fig1) Generally, the hatching success increased with time, but declined with increase in salinity level. However, there was no hatching in 10ppt. Hatching occurred in 2, 4 and 6ppt 23hrs after incubation whereas in 0 and 8ppt hatching occurred about an hr later. In 8ppt the hatched larvae did not survive beyond four and half hrs after hatching. Hatching success differed at the various incubation salinities (Table 1) and time intervals ($p < 0.05$).

Salinity Tolerance of seven day-old fry (*C. gariepinus* x *H bidorsalis*)

The cumulative mortality of the seven day-old fry transferred into various salinities increased with exposure salinity and duration. All fry transferred into 10ppt died at the 8th hr, whereas those in 8ppt died 16hrs later (Fig 2.). In none of the other salinities was 100% mortality recorded. No mortality was recorded in the control

(0ppt). Details of results of median lethal salinity and median lethal time (Table 2 and 3) indicated that the 96hr median lethal salinity (MLS-96) was 4.39ppt, half that of 6ppt whereas the MLT_{50} for 2ppt was 578.33hrs which was 258 times that of 10ppt (2.24hrs). The cumulative mortality of the graded salinities differed whereas that of time intervals at 24-96hrs did not differ but differed at 3-12 hrs $p < 0.05$ (Table 4).

DISCUSSION

The results of the present study showed that hatching of (*C. gariepinus* x *H. bidorsalis*) eggs occurred within salinities (0 to 8ppt) with most favorable range of 0-4ppt. This hatching range was not quite different from the cross of *C. gariepinus* 0-7ppt, with optimum range of 0-5ppt (Gbulubo and Erundu, 1998) and cross of *H. longifilis* 0-7.5ppt with optimum range of 0-4.5ppt (Fashina - Bombata and Busari, 2003). The body fluid of *C. gariepinus* has been found to be 280 (20)_m OSm/kg which is equivalent to 9.5ppt salinity (Britz and Hecht, 1989). It thus appear that the eggs of *C. gariepinus* are hypo-osmotic to the body fluid of the parent, and are not capable of surviving in salinity beyond 8ppt This may explain the death of the hatched larvae in 8ppt about 4 ½ hrs later.

The cumulative mortality of the seven day-old fry transferred into the various salinities increased with exposure salinity and duration. This appears to be characteristic of freshwater stenohaline fish, decreasing survival rate with increasing salinity. They are unable to maintain a constant concentration of body salts as the external salinity rises to concentrations iso-osmotic and hyperosmotic to their body fluid concentration (Davis and Simco, 1976; Goswami *et al.*, 1983). This may be due to increasing maintenance requirements at higher salinities (Brett, 1979; Kilambi, 1980).

The salinity tolerance of the African catfish hybrid eggs and fry are of special interest in aquaculture. Catfish farmers in brackish water environment should restrict breeding or spawning of *C. gariepinus* x *H. bidorsalis* to areas with salinity not above 4ppt for meaningful economic advantage in production. Fish farmers can stock their ponds directly within salinities not above 4ppt with fry raised in freshwater. However, growth performance of the fry within this salinity range needs to be investigated before culture is adopted. Britz and Hecht (1989), recommended the raising of catfish larvae in low salinities ≤ 5 ppt as preventive measure against pathogen infection.

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Fig. 1 Percentage hatchability of African catfish hybrid (*C.gariepinus* ♀ × *H. bidorsalis* ♂) eggs incubated in different salinities.

Table 1 Hatchability (%) of eggs of African catfish hybrid (*C.gariepinus* x *H. bidorsalis*) in (a) various incubation salinities and (b) duration (means \pm SD, n =3)

(a) Salinity (‰)	Hatchability	(b)Duration (hrs)	Hatchability
0	27.37 \pm 23.00 ^a	23	0.07 \pm 0.26 ⁱ
2	24.09 \pm 20.52 ^b	24	0.44 \pm 0.29 ⁱ
4	26.62 \pm 22.18 ^a	25	3.20 \pm 0.29 ^h
6	21.07 \pm 16.42 ^c	26	8.56 \pm 5.50 ^g
8	16.81 \pm 13.67 ^d	27	15.11 \pm 7.83 ^f
10	0.00 \pm 0.00 ^e	28	21.52 \pm 10.81 ^e
		29	28.39 \pm 14.75 ^d
		30	35.0 \pm 17.5 ^c
		31	38.93 \pm 20.51 ^b
		32	42.06 \pm 22.73 ^a

NB: Means with similar alphabets in the same column are not significantly different ($p > 0.05$) for salinity and duration respectively

Fig. 2 Cumulative mortality (%) of 7 day-old fry of African catfish hybrid (*C. gariepinus* ♀ × *H. bidorsalis* ♂) transferred from 0ppt to higher salinity for 96hrs

Table 2 Median lethal salinity and associated 95% (lower and upper confidence limits) of 7 day-old hybrid fry (*C. gariepinus* x *H. bidorsalis*)

Duration (Hrs)	MLS ₅	MLS ₅₀	MLS ₈₅	MLS ₉₀	MLS ₉₅	MLS ₉₉
6	7.18(4.6 – 8.02)	9.01(8.23-9.95)	10.17(9.41-12.26)	10.44(9.62-12.87)	10.85(9.92-13.8)	11.6(10.45-15.57)
12	4.6(3.71-5.17)	6.72(6.33-7.10)	8.05(7.61-8.68)	8.36(7.89-9.09)	8.83(8.23-9.70)	9.70(8.10-10.87)
24	2.65(1.80-3.22)	4.95(4.56-5.36)	6.40(5.94-7.07)	6.75(6.23-7.50)	7.25(6.67-8.15)	8.21(7.46-9.38)
48	2.61(1.84-3.11)	4.49(4.13-4.86)	5.67(5.25-6.28)	5.95(5.59-6.65)	6.36(5.84-7.19)	7.14(6.48-8.23)
72	2.55(1.77-3.05)	4.44(4.08-4.82)	5.64(5.23-6.26)	5.92(5.46-6.62)	6.30(5.81-7.17)	7.12(6.46-8.22)
96	2.49(1.70-2.99)	4.39(4.04-4.77)	5.60(5.18-6.23)	5.88(5.43-6.59)	6.31(5.78-7.15)	7.10(6.43-8.20)

Table 3 Median lethal time to death and associated 95% (lower and upper confidence limits) of 7 day – old hybrid fry (*C. gariepinus* x *H. bidorsalis*)

Salinity (ppt)	MLT ₅	MLT ₅₀	MLT ₈₅	MLT ₉₀	MLT ₉₅	MLT ₉₉
	72.71	578.33	896.92	972.27	1083.95	1293.44
	4.83	124.94	200.62	218.51	245.04	294.80
	-21.77	22.18	49.87	56.42	66.12	84.33
	4.4.97(2.49-6.38)	9.62(8.62-10.65)	12.55(11.41-14.40)	13.24(11.99-15.37)	14.27(12.83-16.83)	16.20(14.36-19.61)
	-3.58	2.24	5.91	6.77	8.06	10.47

Table 4 Cumulative mortality (%) of 7 day-old fry of (*C. gariepinus* x *H. bidorsalis*) exposed to (a) graded salinities at (b) various intervals

(a) Salinity (ppt)	Cumulative Mortality	95% confidence limit		(b) Duration (hrs)	Cumulative Mortality	95% confidence limit	
		Lower bound	Upper bound			Lower bound	Upper bound
2	0.13 ^e	- 0.19	0.44	3	1.05 ^d	0.65	1.45
4	1.41 ^d	1.10	1.71	6	1.94 ^c	1.56	2.32
6	6.12 ^c	5.81	6.43	12	4.30 ^b	3.90	4.70
8	7.38 ^b	7.07	7.68	24	5.90 ^a	5.51	6.29
10	9.22 ^a	8.91	9.52	36	6.40 ^a	6.01	6.79
				48	6.35 ^a	5.96	6.74
				72	6.40 ^a	6.01	6.79
				96	6.45 ^a	6.06	6.84

NB Means with similar alphabets in the same column are not significantly different (p>0.05) for salinity and duration respectively

Table 5 Water quality parameters of the different test salinities during egg incubation

Salinity (‰)	Temperature (°C)		Dissolved Oxygen (mg/l)		pH	
	Range	Mean	Range	Mean	Range	Mean
0	23.0-24.0	23.58±0.44	6.4-6.8	6.55±0.16	5.8-6.2	6.0±0.14
2	23.0-24.0	23.66±0.37	6.4-6.6	6.5±0.1	5.6-6.6	5.9±0.34
4	23.0-24.0	23.41±0.44	6.2-6.6	6.4±0.14	5.6-6.6	5.9±0.34
6	23.0-24.0	23.41±0.44	6.2-6.8	6.45±0.21	5.8-6.2	6.1±0.16
8	23.0-24.0	23.33±0.37	6.4-6.8	6.55±0.16	5.8-6.2	6.1±0.16
10	23.0-24.0	23.33±0.37	6.2-6.4	6.35±0.08	6.6-6.4	6.4±0.09

Table 6 Water quality parameters of the different test salinities for 7 day-old fry of African catfish hybrid (*C gariepinus* × *H. bidorsalis*) (mean ±SD)

Salinity (‰)	Temperature (°C)		Dissolved Oxygen (mg/l)		pH	
	Range	Mean	Range	Mean	Range	Mean
0	26.0-27.0	26.33±0.37	5.8-6.0	5.85±0.08	5.8-6.2	6.0±0.14
2	26.0-27.0	26.33±0.37	5.8-6.0	5.8±0.14	5.4-6.0	5.8±0.24
4	26.0-27.0	26.75±0.25	5.8-6.0	5.95±0.08	5.6-6.2	5.9±0.22
6	26.5- 27.0	26.58±0.34	5.8-6.2	6.0±0.14	5.8-6.2	6.0±0.76
8	26.5-27.0	26.75±0.25	6.2-6.4	6.2±0.14	5.6-6.2	6.0±0.24
10	26.0-27.0	26.66±0.37	6.2-6.4	6.35±0.08	5.6-6.0	5.8±0.14

Received for Publication: 27/04/2012

Accepted for Publication: 26/06/2012

Corresponding author

Gbulubo, A. J.

African Regional Aquaculture Centre, Nigerian Institute for Oceanography and Marine Research, P M. B 5122, Port Harcourt, Nigeria